

IMPORTANT FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONS IN SUBSOIL INDUSTRY*Salkynov A.**MBA, DBA Doctoral Student**Almaty Management University, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

The essence of the economic system of subsoil use is examined, including its content, elements, and features in a mixed economy. Particular emphasis is placed on the evolution of economic theory and the role of the state as the primary regulator of economic entities operating in the mineral resource complex and its infrastructure. The text illustrates the role of modern economic theory as a science in developing and justifying the principles of the territorial-economic system of subsoil use, both theoretically and practically.

Keywords: subsurface use sector, subsurface use management, subsurface use management mechanisms, organizational and economic mechanisms, small and medium-sized subsurface use organizations.

The economic system of subsoil use is a historically established and enshrined in law, operating in the subsoil use sector as a set of principles, rules, and norms that determine the form and content of the main economic relations between entities arising in the process of production, distribution, exchange, and consumption of economic products obtained from the subsoil. In practical terms, it represents a specially organized system of relations between economic entities that directly or indirectly ensure the production, distribution, exchange, and consumption of resources naturally found in the earth's subsoil.

The functioning of the economic system of subsoil use should be aimed at fulfilling the most important socio-economic tasks of society:

- ensuring the economic growth of all entities involved in subsoil use;
- coordinating all types of economic activity in the field of subsoil use;
- creating favorable socio-economic conditions that contribute to improving the quality of life in the country and region; complying not only with the country's industrial policy, but also creating favorable conditions for the implementation of the social goals of the entire national economy [1].

An important characteristic of the economic system of the subsoil use sector is that it covers the entire set of economic relations arising in the process of human interaction with the earth's resources in order to transform them into elements of life. That is why the functioning of the subsoil use sector is linked to the emergence of many social problems in society, and not only of an economic nature.

It is well known that the subsoil use sector generates the most significant portion of funds at the national level. However, this raises a legitimate question: how effectively and fairly are these funds being used?

The state protects its rights as the owner and creates conditions and prerequisites to ensure that the processes of development and use of non-renewable mineral resources are in the public interest. The current situation in the field of subsoil use in Kazakhstan, on the contrary, illustrates what can happen when the system of basic and complementary institutions that determine the norms, rules, and procedures for involving subsoil resources in economic circulation is incomplete. As a

result, the interests of the controlling shareholders of subsoil user companies have been taken into account in the process of developing and using mineral resources, rather than the interests of society.

On the other hand, social factors play a very important role in the dynamics of innovative development in the field of subsoil use. Without changing the essential nature of the economic system of subsoil use, its content is transformed in the process of its development. Both the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of economic entities elements of the system and the content and forms of interaction between them change.

The economic system of subsoil use involves not only economic processes based on the property relations that have developed in the relevant subsoil use sectors. This system also involves organizational and management processes based on the diversity and development of various organizational and legal forms of economic activity of entities in the subsoil use sector, as well as direct production processes that ensure the extraction, enrichment, transportation, etc. of land resources. Therefore, from our point of view, the economic system of the subsoil use sector is only a component (albeit a very important one) of the complex economic system of the subsoil use sector. The results of research conducted over the past two decades confirm the fact that in practice there are no purely economic (and even less so financial) mechanisms for subsoil use: there are organizational and economic, organizational and managerial, economic and managerial mechanisms, etc [2].

The economic system of subsoil use is an eco-socio-economic system. Its economic goals cannot and should not be achieved without addressing environmental and social issues. However, these tasks are often associated with the implementation of certain types of non-economic efficiency, which in some cases contradict traditional, generally accepted criteria of economic efficiency. At the same time, the current activities of a particular economic entity or its project management are, by their nature, unprofitable or even loss-making. Therefore, in our opinion, assessing the efficiency of the economic system of the subsoil use sector solely from the perspective of profitability and return on investment criteria does not take into account the usefulness of many types of infrastructure activities that create the necessary conditions for its normal functioning

[3]. In turn, a reliable system for supporting core activities is necessary for the effective operation of the main production units of subsoil use companies and their economic efficiency as a necessary condition for economic growth not only at the micro level, but also for improving the quality of life in the relevant region and the country as a whole, at all levels of economic management.

The functioning of the economic system of the subsoil use sector is a set of interactions between its elements - economic entities linked by certain relationships, among which financial and legal relationships occupy a central place. At the same time, the forms of ownership of the interacting economic entities may vary. Their coexistence is the basis for the development of various organizational and economic forms of public-private partnership [4].

Under the general laws of globalization and integration of the world economy, the laws governing the functioning of the economic system of subsoil use extend beyond its internal environment and beyond the system itself. From this perspective, issues related to the functioning of the internal market of the territorial-economic system of subsoil use take a back seat. Small and medium-sized businesses in the subsoil use sector occupy a modest position for objective reasons, while the activities of transnational corporations cannot be confined to the rigid boundaries of the relevant territory. Therefore, subsoil use is characterized to a greater extent by inter-country and inter-regional interactions based mainly on commodity-money relations. The internal market within the territorial-economic system of subsoil use, as a closed system, has minimal capacity in reality and in some cases practically does not exist [5].

On the other hand, there are many regions in the national economy with a pronounced raw materials specialization, including single-industry towns and urban-type settlements, whose infrastructure directly depends on the nature of the work of one or two city-forming enterprises. However, even in this case, the financial support of the municipal and social infrastructure of the relevant territory is mainly provided on the basis of inter-country and inter-regional interactions, which can be both inter-sectoral and intra-sectoral in nature.

Modern economic theory reserves for itself the development and justification of the principles of functioning of the territorial-economic system of subsoil use. The practical significance of this work lies, first, in assessing the place of the market in this system alongside existing areas of weakened and completely absent markets in order to identify the forms and scope of economic laws; secondly, in assessing the place and role of

the state in this system at all levels of government; thirdly, in assessing the effectiveness of the functioning of subsoil use enterprises in terms of their impact on the development of the territory and the country as a whole [6].

The results of economic research show that the growth of export prices for mineral resources, on the one hand, creates favorable conditions for the growth of both its revenues and those of the regions and the country as a whole. On the other hand, it “washes out” resources from the territorial-economic system of subsoil use as a closed system and thus reduces the business activity of many domestic enterprises. However, this is not always the case. According to the results of even more global studies, it should be noted that internal and external interactions can behave in three ways: dominate each other, compete with each other, or support each other. All these interactions are usually of a flow nature. Therefore, in some cases, we may be talking not about individual interactions, but about flows of interactions.

Based on an analysis of the key determinants of the modern development of economic systems and the economic system of subsoil use, in particular, it can be concluded that research into the economic system of subsoil use should be based on the integration of closely interrelated political-economic and institutional approaches.

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